

Breaking Barriers: Understanding Dentist's Challenges in Treating Early Childhood Caries in Chhattisgarh

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Abstract

Early Childhood Caries (ECC) remains one of the most prevalent chronic disease affecting young children worldwide. Despite the availability of preventive and restorative treatment options many children still remain untreated due to various barriers encountered by dental professionals. The present study aimed to evaluate the challenges faced by dentists while managing early childhood caries and to compare the attitudes of general dentists and paediatric dentists towards treating children. A cross-sectional survey was conducted using a structured questionnaire distributed among dental practitioners. The questionnaire assessed multiple domains including child coping ability, dentist perception of treatment stress, time constraint and attitude towards restoring primary teeth. Statistical analysis was performed to compare responses between general dentists and paediatric dentists. The results indicated that general dentists reported higher stress levels, greater preference for referring child patients, and less confidence in managing paediatric dental procedures compared to paediatric dentists. However, no significant differences were observed in some domains related to perceptions of children coping abilities. The findings highlight the need for improved training, continuing education, and behavioural management skill development among general dentists to enhance paediatric dental care delivery. Addressing these challenges may contribute to better management of ECC and improved oral health outcomes among children.

Keywords

Early childhood caries, Paediatric Dentistry, Dentist attitude, Dental anxiety, Dental practice challenges, Behaviour management

Introduction

Early Childhood Caries (ECC) is defined as the presence of one or more decayed, missing, or filled tooth surfaces in any primary tooth in a child aged 71 months or younger^[1]. ECC is characterized by rapid progression of dental caries that may affect multiple teeth soon after eruption^[2]. In many cases, the lesions develop on tooth surfaces that are generally less susceptible to caries in older children and adults^[3].

ECC is considered a major public health concern affecting both developing and developed nations^[4]. Studies have demonstrated that untreated dental caries in early childhood can result in pain, infection, difficulty in eating and impaired growth and development^[5]. Additionally, poor oral health during early childhood may negatively influence the quality of life of both children and their caregivers^[6].

Despite increasing awareness regarding preventive oral health measures, utilization of dental services among preschool children remains inadequate^[7]. One of the factors contributing to this issue is the reluctance of dental practitioners to treat young children due to behavioural challenges and time constraints. The management of paediatric patients often require specialized skills in behaviour guidance and communication, which may not always be adequately emphasized during undergraduate training^[8,9].

Previous studies have suggested that general dentists may experience greater difficulty in treating young children compared to paediatric dentists who are specifically trained in child behaviour management. Factors such as treatment stress, limited clinical time, lack of confidence in restorative procedures for primary teeth, and preference for referral to specialists have been reported as common barriers^[10,11].

Understanding the perceptions and challenges faced by dental practitioners is essential for improving the delivery of paediatric dental care. Therefore, the present study aimed to assess dentist's attitude and challenges in managing early childhood caries and to compare responses between general dentists and paediatric dentists practicing in Chhattisgarh.

Materials and Method

A cross-sectional questionnaire-based study was conducted for the duration of 3 months to assess dentist's attitude towards managing early childhood caries. The individuals who will provide voluntary informed consent, registered General dental practitioner and Paedodontist practicing in Chhattisgarh will be included in this study. The registered dentists who were not into clinical practice will be excluded.

A questionnaire with closed-ended questions will be randomly distributed to 96 dentists (48 general dentists and 48 paediatric dentists). Each dentist will complete the Barriers to Childhood Caries Treatment (BaCCT) questionnaire, which includes 22 factors that evaluates barriers across five domains (Fig. 1):

Responses will be collected using Google Forms and will be analysed statistically to identify any correlations among the variables.

Dentists will be asked to rate their level of agreement with each statement on a 5-point Likert scale (1 - Strongly Disagree; 2 - Disagree; 3 - Neither Agree

nor Disagree; 4 - Agree; 5 - Strongly Agree), regarding dental care for preschool children (≤ 5 years old). Items with a value >3 were considered barriers perceived by dentists.

<p>Domain-I (Child coping abilities)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Children get upset easily 2. Cannot cope well with treatment 3. Do not like sitting in the dental chair 4. Cannot accept dental treatment 5. Most children are fearful of treatment 6. Do not like the sound of drill <p>Domain-II (Attitude toward offering restorative treatment)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do not like giving local anaesthetic to children 2. Prefer to refer children to be treated by other colleagues 3. Find filling children's teeth stressful 4. Rarely have enough time to spend with child patients 5. I enjoy filling children's teeth 6. Feel apprehensive if I have to do a filling in a child 7. Providing dental treatment for children is troublesome <p>Domain-III (Attitude toward the necessity of restoring primary teeth)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I feel there is no reason to fill primary teeth 2. If decayed primary molars not causing any symptom, they are best left untreated 3. I do not fill cavities in children who attend regularly 4. The time it would take to fill primary teeth would be better spent with other patients 5. On the whole, decayed primary teeth are best left untreated, rather than filled 6. I do not fill cavities in children who are not regular attenders 7. I feel there is little point in filling primary teeth <p>Domain-IV (Parent's expectation)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. If a child has toothache, parents are more likely to ask for extractions 2. If a child had a decayed molar, parents would expect it to be extracted 3. Parents do not want dentists to fill their children's decayed teeth 4. Parents expect dentists to fill their children's decayed teeth 5. Parents do not see the need for filling primary teeth <p>Domain-V (Existing healthcare system)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The payment I would receive for putting a filling in Primary tooth is inadequate 2. The payment I receive for providing preventive care to children is inadequate 3. The dental care for young children puts more emphasis on fillings rather than prevention 4. I feel that the dental care in India provides a good service for young children

Fig. 1 Barriers to Childhood Caries Treatment (BaCCT) questionnaire

Statistical Analysis

The data are tabulated in Microsoft excel and analysed with SPSS V.24 software. The variables are presented with frequency and percentage. Chi square test is used for the statistical analysis. The p value ≤ 0.05 is considered statistically significant.

Results

The responses obtained from participating dentists were analysed.

The overall Barriers to Childhood Caries Treatment (BaCCT) score across all domains was significantly higher among general dentists when compared to paediatric dentists. On evaluation of the overall mean BaCCT score of individual domains, it was noted that general dentists had significantly higher mean score when compared to paediatric dentists for Domains II and III ($P > 0.05$).

Domain-I	General Dentist	Pedodontist	P value
1. Children get upset easily	3.45 ± 0.81	3.53 ± 0.94	0.646
2. Cannot cope well with treatment	3.02 ± 0.99	3.18 ± 0.81	0.397
3. Do not like sitting in the dental chair	3.41 ± 1.02	3.33 ± 0.77	0.675
4. Cannot accept dental treatment	3.14 ± 0.92	3.2 ± 0.87	0.732
5. Most children are fearful of treatment	3.61 ± 0.98	3.76 ± 0.8	0.425
6. Do not like the sound of drill	3.96 ± 0.87	4.09 ± 0.76	0.448
Domain-II	General Dentist	Pedodontist	P value
1. Do not like giving local anaesthetic to children	3.33 ± 1.05	3.31 ± 1.06	0.918
2. Prefer to refer children to be treated by other colleagues	2.51 ± 0.95	2.07 ± 0.96	0.025*
3. Find filling children's teeth stressful	3.06 ± 1.1	2.56 ± 1.12	0.029*
4. Rarely have enough time to spend with child patients	3.18 ± 0.99	2.67 ± 0.98	0.013*
5. I enjoy filling children's teeth	3.39 ± 0.9	4.16 ± 0.56	0.000***
6. Feel apprehensive if I have to do a filling in a child	3.2 ± 0.85	2.69 ± 1.26	0.021*
7. Providing dental treatment for children is troublesome	3.08 ± 1.02	2.76 ± 1.15	0.148
Domain-III	General Dentist	Pedodontist	P value
1. I feel there is no reason to fill primary teeth	2.16 ± 1.12	1.91 ± 1.12	0.287
2. If decayed primary molars not causing any symptom, they are best left untreated	2.16 ± 0.99	2.11 ± 1.03	0.825
3. I do not fill cavities in children who attend regularly	2.37 ± 0.98	2.36 ± 1.17	0.938
4. The time it would take to fill primary teeth would be better spent with other patients	2.27 ± 0.92	2.09 ± 1.2	0.394
5. On the whole, decayed primary teeth are best left untreated, rather than filled	2.2 ± 1.02	2.02 ± 1.2	0.444
6. I do not fill cavities in children who are not regular attenders	2.39 ± 0.94	2.02 ± 1.12	0.041*
7. I feel there is little point in filling primary teeth	3.12 ± 0.99	2.36 ± 1.25	0.001**
Domain-IV	General Dentist	Pedodontist	P value
1. If a child has toothache, parents are more likely to ask for extractions	3.37 ± 0.89	3.27 ± 0.94	0.573
2. If a child had a decayed molar, parents would expect it to be extracted	3.35 ± 1.02	3.2 ± 0.92	0.444
3. Parents do not want dentists to fill their children's decayed teeth	2.98 ± 1.17	2.8 ± 0.84	0.395
4. Parents expect dentists to fill their children's decayed teeth	3.65 ± 0.89	3.62 ± 0.83	0.889
5. Parents do not see the need for filling primary teeth	3.33 ± 1.11	3.36 ± 1.03	0.919
Domain-V	General Dentist	Pedodontist	P value
1. The payment I would receive for putting a filling in Primary tooth is inadequate	3.14 ± 0.89	3.36 ± 0.88	0.233
2. The payment I receive for providing preventive care to children is inadequate	3.06 ± 0.99	3.33 ± 1.13	0.207
3. The dental care for young children puts more emphasis on fillings rather than prevention	3.33 ± 1.16	2.96 ± 1.02	0.096
4. I feel that the dental care in India provides a good service for young children	3.51 ± 0.97	3.13 ± 1.06	0.072

Fig. 2 Comparison based on items of individual domains

Domain I – Child Coping Abilities

Fig. 3 Domain I – Child Coping Abilities

No statistically significant difference was observed in the mean BaCCT scores between general dentists and paediatric dentists regarding perceptions of children’s coping abilities ($p > 0.05$) (Fig. 3).

Domain II – Attitude toward offering restorative treatment

Fig. 4 Domain II- Attitude toward offering restorative treatment

In Domain-II, the mean BaCCT scores were significantly higher among general dentists when compared to paediatric dentists, when it came to questions pertaining to prefer to refer children to be treated by other colleagues, find filling children’s teeth stressful, rarely have enough time to spend with child patients, enjoy filling children’s teeth and feel apprehensive to do a filling in a child ($P < 0.05$) (Fig. 4).

Domain III – Attitude toward the necessity of restoring primary teeth

In Domain-III, the mean BaCCT scores were significantly higher among general dentists when compared to paediatric dentists, when it came to questions pertaining to not filling cavities in children who are not regular attenders and feel there is little point in filling primary teeth ($P < 0.05$) (Fig. 5).

Domain IV and V

In Domains IV and V, no significant difference in the mean BaCCT scores was observed among general dentists when compared to paediatric dentists, when it came to the questions pertaining to the parent’s expectation toward the treatment of early childhood caries and their views toward the existing healthcare system ($P > 0.05$) (Fig. 6 & 7).

Fig. 5 Domain III- Attitude toward the necessity of restoring primary teeth

Fig. 6 Domain IV- Parent's expectation

Fig. 7 Domain V- Existing Healthcare System

Discussion

Early childhood caries (ECC) is the most prevalent chronic diseases affecting children globally and is influenced by multiple factors including diet, oral hygiene practices, microbial activity, and socioeconomic conditions. Drury et al. [1] and Petersen [2] reported that ECC remains a major public health concern worldwide. The dentist attitude towards treating paediatric patients play an important role in determining the accessibility and quality of dental care for children. The present study compared the attitudes of general dentists and paediatric dentists toward managing children with dental caries and identified several notable differences between the two groups.

In the present study, no statistically significant difference was observed between general dentists and paediatric dentists in Domain I, which evaluated children’s coping abilities during dental treatment. Both groups agreed that children frequently become upset during dental procedures and may have difficulty coping with treatment. These findings are consistent with previous research by Klingberg and Broberg [7], who reported that dental fear and behaviour management problems are common among paediatric patients and can significantly influence treatment outcomes. Similarly, Townend et al. [14] reported that unfamiliar dental environments and instruments can contribute to anxiety among children during dental visits. Dental anxiety in children is often associated with fear of pain, dental instruments, and previous negative experiences, as described by Cuthbert and Melamed [15]. Furthermore, Gustafsson et al. [16] reported that dental fear experienced during childhood may persist into adulthood if not managed effectively.

The present study also evaluated dentist attitude towards performing restorative procedures in children. Paediatric dentists reported significantly greater enjoyment and confidence in performing restorative treatments compared to general dentists. This finding is similar to the observations of Brickhouse et al. [8], who reported that dentists with specialized paediatric training demonstrate greater confidence in treating young children. Paediatric dentists are trained in various behaviour management techniques such as tell-show-do, distraction, and positive reinforcement, which help to improve children's cooperation during treatment. These techniques have been well described by Wright and Kupietzky [17] in paediatric dental practice.

In contrast, general dentists in the present study reported greater apprehension when performing restorative procedures in children. This observation is consistent with the findings of Casamassimo [9], who highlighted that general dentists often feel less prepared to manage paediatric patients due to limited training in behaviour guidance during undergraduate education. Similarly, Seale and Casamassimo [6] reported that general dentists frequently refer paediatric patients to specialists due to difficulties in behaviour management and time constraints.

Time constraints were also identified as an important factor influencing dentists' attitudes toward paediatric dental care. Many dentists indicated that treating children often requires additional time because of the need for behavioural guidance and communication with both the child and the parents. Similar findings were reported by Gussy et al. [18], who emphasized that paediatric dental treatment frequently requires more time compared to adult dental care.

Another important finding of the present study was the difference in attitudes regarding the restoration of primary teeth. Paediatric dentists demonstrated stronger agreement regarding the importance of restoring carious primary teeth compared to general dentists. Berkowitz [10] emphasized that early childhood caries can progress rapidly and may lead to extensive destruction of primary dentition if not treated promptly. Untreated carious lesions in primary teeth may result in pain, infection, premature tooth loss, and disturbances in the eruption of permanent teeth, as reported by Casamassimo et al. [3] and Tinanoff and Reisine [19]. Furthermore, Sheiham [4] reported that untreated dental caries in young children can negatively affect their nutrition, growth, and quality of life.

Parental expectations also play an important role in determining treatment decisions. In the present study, many dentists believed that parents sometimes prefer extraction rather than restorative treatment when a child experiences tooth pain. Similar findings were reported by Pine et al. [12], who found that parental beliefs and awareness regarding the importance of primary teeth significantly influence dental treatment decisions for children. However, increasing awareness regarding paediatric oral health has led some parents to expect restorative treatment for decayed primary teeth.

Preventive strategies are essential in controlling the burden of ECC. Featherstone [13] described dental caries as a dynamic disease process that can be prevented through fluoride therapy, dietary modifications, and effective oral hygiene practices. Preventive interventions such as fluoride varnish

application and sealants have been shown to significantly reduce the incidence of dental caries in children, as reported by Marinho ^[21]. Additionally, Ramos-Gomez et al. ^[22] emphasized the importance of early preventive interventions and parental counseling in reducing the risk of ECC.

Public health initiatives focusing on prevention and early intervention are therefore essential to reduce the global burden of ECC, particularly in developing countries where access to dental care may be limited, as highlighted by Petersen ^[2] and Dye et al. ^[23].

Overall, the findings of the present study indicate that paediatric dentists demonstrate more positive attitudes and greater confidence in managing paediatric patients compared to general dentists. These differences are likely due to specialized training and greater clinical exposure to children during postgraduate education. Strengthening undergraduate dental education and promoting continuing professional development programs for general dentists may improve their confidence in treating paediatric patients, as suggested by Harris et al. ^[24], Watt ^[25], Griffin et al. ^[26], Ismail and Sohn ^[27], and Fontana and Gonzalez-Cabezas ^[28]. Such initiatives may ultimately contribute to improved oral health outcomes for children.

Conclusion

Early childhood caries remains a significant oral health challenge among young children. The present study demonstrated that general dentists experience greater stress and hesitation while treating paediatric patients compared to paediatric dentists. Factors such as lack of confidence, time constraints, and preference for referral contribute to the challenges faced in managing ECC. Enhancing paediatric dental training during undergraduate education and providing continuing professional development programs may improve dentists' confidence and willingness to treat children. Addressing these barriers is essential for improving access to dental care and reducing the burden of early childhood caries.

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